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Applying INSPIRE to quantify a detail cost of restrictions in road and rail infrastructure using time-space analysis

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Goal

Introduction

Railways capacity

Problem description

Topology Features

Application of INSPIRE Transport Model

3D Space-Time Feature representation

Solution

Develop a procedure to compute detailed impact of different events on railways and road capacity, using INSPIRE and other interoperable models

Introduction – Spanish railways network

MAPA 1

ÁREAS TERRITORIALES OPERATIVAS DE ADIF

“Capacity is a measure of the ability to move a specific amount of traffic over a defined rail line with a given set of resources under a specific service plan.’

Krueger, H., 1999. Parametric modelling in rail capacity planning. In: Proceedings of the 1999 Winter Simulation Conference, pp. 1194–2000

Definition depends on scope

Market (customer needs)	Infrastructure planning	Timetable planning	Operations
<p>expected number of train paths (peak)</p> <p>expected mix of traffic and speed (peak)</p> <p>infrastructure quality need</p> <p>journey times as short as possible</p> <p>translation of all short and long-term market-induced demands to reach optimised load</p>	<p>expected number of train paths (average)</p> <p>expected mix of traffic and speed (average)</p> <p>expected conditions of infrastructure</p> <p>time supplements for expected disruptions</p> <p>maintenance strategies</p>	<p>requested number of train paths</p> <p>requested mix of traffic and speed</p> <p>existing conditions of infrastructure</p> <p>time supplements for expected disruptions</p> <p>time supplements for maintenance</p> <p>connecting services in stations</p> <p>requests out of regular interval timetables (system times, train stops, ...)</p>	<p>actual number of trains</p> <p>actual mix of traffic and speed</p> <p>actual conditions of infrastructure</p> <p>delays caused by operational disruptions</p> <p>delays caused by track works</p> <p>delays caused by missed connections</p> <p>additional capacity by time supplements not needed</p>

The capacity of any railway infrastructure is:

The total number of possible paths in a defined time window, considering the actual path mix or known developments respectively and the IM's own assumptions;

In nodes, individual lines or part of the network;

With market-oriented quality.

Theoretical Capacity is the number of trains that could run over a route, during a specific time interval, mathematically calculated using an empirical formula. It represents an upper limit for line capacity.

Practical Capacity represents the practical limit of the number of trains (usually considering the current train mix, priorities, traffic bunching, etc.) that can be moved on a line in order to guarantee a reasonable level of reliability. It is a more realistic measure than theoretical capacity, usually around 60%-75% of the latter.

Used Capacity is the actual traffic volume over the network, usually lower than the practical capacity.

Available Capacity is the difference between the Used Capacity and the Practical Capacity and provides an useful indication of additional trains that could be handled by the network.

Introduction – Railways capacity

Factors to take into account in Capacity computing

- Number of vehicles or trains
- Train calification
- Timetables
- Speed restrictions length
- Speed restrictions types
- Speed restriction scheduling

Weather impact over capacity

PESETA II Project, Transport and climate change study,
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When a speed restriction is applied to the infrastructure, the schedule of trains is affected

Actual impact based on alphanumeric attributes and relational databases

Difficult computing in real time. Complex offline software

No possibility to take advantage of geospatial attributes

AVE				Tipo: 300								
Números de marcha				2121		2131		2141				
Bloqueo	Sit Km	VMáx	Dependencia	C	Hora	T	C	Hora	T	C	Hora	T
	470.5		SEVILLA-SANTA JUSTA.....		12.45			13.45			14.45	
	469.7	30	KM. 469,651.....	o	12.47			13.47			14.47	
	468.7	80	KM. 468,657.....	o	12.48			13.48			14.48	
	465.9	100	KM. 465,922.....	o	12.50			13.50			14.50	
	465.5	140	KM. 465,483.....	o	12.50	½		13.50	½		14.50	½
	462.1	180	KM. 462,069.....	o	12.52			13.52			14.52	½
	460.4		MAJARABIQUE.....	o	12.52	½		13.52	½		14.53	
	426.1		GUADAJOZ.....	o	13.01			14.01	½		15.01	½
	408.9	250	PEÑAFLORE.....	o	13.05	½		14.06			15.06	
	394.4		KM. 394,4.....	o	13.09			14.10			15.10	
	387.1		HORNACHUELOS.....	o	13.11			14.11	½		15.11	½
	368.9		KM. 368,859.....	o	13.15	½		14.16			15.16	
	363.6	220	KM. 363,569.....	o	13.17			14.17	½		15.17	½
	362.9		ALMODOVAR.....	o	13.17	½		14.18			15.18	
	358.0	250	BIF. MALAGA-A. V.....	o	13.19			14.20			15.20	

↓ Par			Servicio de las estaciones Fechas y motivos de las limitaciones	Impar ↑		
Km.	Velocidad	Tiempo concedido.		Tiempo concedido.	Velocidad	Km.
			<p>LINARES-BAEZA</p> <p>Comunicación de "Marche el Tren por Radiotelefonía" a los Trenes de Mercancías. (art. 248.1 RGC).</p> <p>Todas las circulaciones a su paso por Vía 7, zona de báscula, no excederán de 30 Km/h, excepto las pesadas al paso cuya Velocidad Máxima será de 13 Km/h.</p> <p>LAS MADRIGUERAS</p>			
3	60	0,9	Inundaciones (13-09-07).	0,9	60	323,000
						323,300
4	60	0,8	Inundaciones (06-12-10). Señalizada al lado IZQUIERDO para trenes IMPARES.	0,8	60	324,550
						324,750
5	60	0,8	<p>JABALQUINTO</p> <p>Inundaciones (04-11-12). Señalizada al lado IZQUIERDO para trenes IMPARES.</p> <p>ESPELUY</p>	0,8	60	329,050
						329,220
6	60	H	Daños en terraplén por lluvias (05-03-10). Señalizada al lado IZQUIERDO para trenes PARES.	H	60	346,450

PostGIS
GDAL
Python
QGIS

Leaflet framework
Geoserver
OGC WMTS server

Vehicle kinematics

Solution – Typical vehicle reaction

Increase time due to a speed restriction

Solution – Kinematic vehicle reaction

Diferencia Norma Tecnica - Teorico

$dt = -0.5 \text{ m/s}^2$ $at = 0.6 \text{ m/s}^2$

Diferencia Norma Tecnica - Teorico

$dt = -0.3 \text{ m/s}^2$ $at = 0.4 \text{ m/s}^2$

$$T_{ltv} = \frac{V_{ltv} - V_{max}}{dt} + \frac{L_{ltv} + L_{tr}}{V_{ltv}} + \frac{V_{max} - V_{ltv}}{at}$$

MEDIA DISTANCIA		CERCANIAS	
Serie	Length	Serie	Length
S-448	78,530	462	44,800
S-449	89,970	463	65,550
S-470	79,590	464	80,300
S-592	70,214	465	98,500
S-594	74,748	446	75,993
S-598	75,930	447	75,993
S-599	75,980	451	80,580

Weigh time

LR	1,0
MD	0,5
Cercanías	0,5
Mercancías	0,25

	Double-Track Line Sections (a ... q)
	Single-Track Line Sections (1-4, 1-5, ...)
	Interlocking
	Station (on Double-Track Line Sections)
	Station (between Single-Track Line Sections)

	Single Track Section
	Double Track Section

España	INSPIRE
Estación	RailwayNode
Estación	RailwaySatationNode
Bifurcación	RailwayNode
Linea	RailwayLine
Area Estación	RailwayYardArea
Tramo	RailwayLink
Zona Seguridad	RailwayArea

Location Features - RailwayNode

Link Features - RailwayLink

Line Features - RailwayLine

Track Features - TrainRailwayLine

Location Features - RailwayNode

Link Features - RailwayLink

Line Features - RailwayLine

Path Features - TrainRailwayLine

3594 TrainRailwayLinks

3D space-time Train Path projections

TrainRailwayLine Feature

Z coordinate
store Time from schedule

1. Create RailwayLink features for every pair of TransportNode from IGN -> PostGIS
2. Create TrainRailwayLine features for every path from its schedule -> PostGIS
3. Define a polygon feature with the interest area as IncidGeom. A speed restriction is defined as a linestring
4. Compute in real time, intersection between TrainRailwayLinks with that IncidGeom

As a result, a set of TrainRailwayLinks is obtained, every one with its train information

Incident between Villarrubia de Córdoba and El Higerón Blue RailwayLink – Red incidence feature

Incident between Villarrubia de Córdoba and El Higerón Blue RailwayLink – Red incidence feature

92 affected trains

92 affected trains

Conclusion - Results

Loss time is the difference between real time and schedule one.

In expression (ri) is infrastructure restriction, and (T) time needed to pass through. Total cost for every RI is computed as a sum of them

$$Tri = \sum_{j=1}^{j=n} Tri_j$$

More accurate results

Compute in teal time

Take into account restrictions from real geometry

Geometry level accuracy instead of section of line

Detailed cost of every restriction for each train

Allows make a decision on infrastructure in a more accurate way

Better security

Interoperable data with European Railways Agency and UIC

Thank you

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